

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF OPTIMIZING STUDENTS' INTELLECTUAL AND COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7971374>

Abstract. *This article talks about the role of intellectual abilities in the professional formation of students.*

Keywords: *ability, student, knowledge, skill, competence, intelligence.*

Introduction. It is a gross psychological defect of a high school teacher to hastily conclude that the student lacks professional knowledge, skills and qualifications system, their stability, formed personal working methods, without seriously examining and diagnosing them. is considered The fact that one or another ability was not recognized by the people around them during childhood, the names of many scientists who later gained deserved fame in the world due to these same abilities are famous in the world, for example, Albert Einstein (the founder of the theory of relativity), Nicholas Lobachevsky (founder of the new direction of geometry) and others did not have evidence that he would grow up to be a genius scientist. Abilities are not reflected in knowledge, skills and qualifications, but in the dynamics of their acquisition. The differences that arise in the process of acquiring the knowledge and skills necessary for the activity make it possible to think about the abilities. Therefore, the conditions for the successful implementation of the individual's activity, which appear in the dynamics of the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications, are considered. Individual psychological characteristics manifested in differences are called abilities. To determine this feature, it is appropriate to analyze some factors;

a) if the sum of certain qualities of a person meets the requirements of the activity he has acquired in a specified period of time, he has the ability for this activity;

b) if a person cannot meet the demands of activity in such situations, psychological qualities, that is, abilities, are absent (very weak). But it does not mean that a person with such characteristics cannot acquire skills and qualifications, but the time to acquire them will be extended.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review). Ability is the individual potential and capabilities of a person. Ability is sharply different from knowledge, if knowledge is considered the result of reading, ability is considered a feature of the psychological and physiological structure of a person. Ability is different from skill. Ability is seen as a gift given to a person. Most scientific sources equate skill with ability. Ability improves in the process of acquisition of skills and competencies by a person. Any type of ability consists of a complex psychological concept of a person, which includes a system of characteristics proportional to the requirements of the activity. Therefore, ability should be understood not as a single characteristic, but as a synthesis of characteristics that can meet the requirements of a person's activity and provide an opportunity to achieve high performance in this activity. The basic characteristic for all abilities is the ability to observe, that is, to understand a person, to be able to see one or another sign from an object, to distinguish. One of the leading features of the ability is to creatively imagine

the essence of things and events. It is a result of the formation and development of a person, but also has a natural source. This natural resource is often referred to as the mind. The mind is manifested in excessive interest, inclination, and desire for a specific activity or many things. Mental targets should be understood as the natural basis of the internal capabilities of abilities. It is the product of enthusiasm, inclination, hard work, hard work, demandingness. Ability is divided into general and special categories. General ability means high mental capacity and development. Ability can be formed naturally and developed based on a specific plan. There are ways to develop the ability through a tendency or aspiration to a certain activity, to identify natural mental targets, to engage in continuous activity under the guidance of a specialist, to use special means of improving the ability, to maximally develop the symptoms of a person's activity, to carry out a special approach to the human personality in harmony with general requirements, and other ways. A high level of ability is manifested in talent and talent. Abilities are, in fact, innate. Although the ability is innate, its development also depends on the social environment.

Analysis and results. Development of intellectual abilities. In general, the mind is understood as a system of all cognitive processes, that is, thinking, emotions, memories, sensations, attention, sensations and imagination. The concept of thinking helps to generalize the behavioral characteristics necessary for a person to adapt to changing life conditions. Determination of the ability to solve life problems, verbal (reading comprehension, biography) and practical knowledge (ability to achieve goals). Thus, the mind can be considered a certain stage of the thinking apparatus. In turn, the ability of intellectual activity is a combination of specific characteristics of perception and processing of incoming information. The structure of human intellectual abilities is as follows:

1. The deposit is based on the structure of the brain.
2. General, equally manifested in any activity - memory, learning, attention.
3. Special - required for certain types of activities. For example, a musical ear or commercial understanding.
4. A group developing on the basis of specific and common goals.
5. Vocational abilities, they are manifested in labor processes. For a long time it was believed that a person is born with a certain consciousness that cannot be changed. Later, it became clear that there are unchanging bases, but we answer most of these skills ourselves.

The most rapid development of intellectual abilities is in managerial activities, of course, everyone began to develop rapidly, accepting at least two people with submissiveness.

Communicative ability is the ability to communicate, which has a special appearance in the field of pedagogical interaction.

In psychological literature, several types of communicative abilities are distinguished: 1) a person's ability to understand a person (assessing a person as a person, his special aspects, motives and needs, considering his external behavior in relation to his internal world, face, hands (l, the ability to "read" body movements) 2) self-awareness of a person (assessment of his knowledge, abilities, character and other aspects, how a person is perceived by others and evaluation by the eyes of others); 3) the ability to correctly assess the communication situation (to observe the current situation, to be able to learn more information about the signs of its manifestation, to pay attention to them, to correctly understand the social and psychological essence of the emerging situation ri perception and evaluation).

Conclusions and recommendations. As an educator, a pedagogue should always consider the students to be an object of education for him. However, the educational relationship will become effective only if the student achieves a free and conscious relationship with the teacher-educator. Regardless of what subject is taught, the main tool of the teacher is vocabulary, he demonstrates his communicative ability based on the power of words. Because being able to speak beautifully and impressively is also an art. The professional skills of a teacher who is deprived of art are not formed.

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